

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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1. Gender equality and gender representation in Italy

Gender equality and gender representation are two important and current issues in Italy, as in many other parts of Europe. Gender representation is a fundamental concept in crucial areas such as history, as it helps to ensure a more inclusive and comprehensive perspective of human experiences. Since its inception, history has often given greater prominence to men's narratives and accomplishments, neglecting or underestimating the voices and contributions of women and other gender minorities. This has led to a distorted view of the past and a lack of awareness of the various facets of historical experiences. Gender representation in history is important to include different perspectives, remove limiting gender stereotypes, make visible new models of reference hitherto silenced, have a more accurate and multifaceted historical framework and value gender equality in different historical eras. Italy has made progresses in addressing gender equality issues, but there are still significant challenges to overcome. Key issues include:

- Wage inequalities. Although Italy has laws against wage discrimination, there is still a pay gap between men and women, often referred to as the "gender pay gap".
- Economic participation. Women in Italy are often underrepresented in leadership positions and decision-making roles in different industries. Work-life balance can be a challenge for women wishing to pursue a career.
- Access to education and opportunities. Although Italian women have access to education, there are still sectors in which they are underrepresented, such as science and technology.

Regarding gender representation today in the specific Italian scenario, there are still several gaps in different contexts: in the political sphere, despite some progress, women are still underrepresented in high-level roles. There have been initiatives to promote more women in politics, but there is still much to be done. In the corporate sphere, Italy faces challenges regarding the presence of women in leadership positions in companies, which can often face difficulties in accessing higher positions. Even in the media and culture, there is often an unbalanced representation of genders and women can be portrayed in a stereotyped or limiting way in the media.

To address these issues, in addition to what Europe has already done, Italy has adopted laws and policies to promote gender equality and representation. From a legislative point of view in Italy there are integral protection measures, whose purpose is to prevent, sanction and eradicate effective inequality between men and women. First, equality between men and women is mentioned in Articles 3, 29, 37 and 51 of the Italian

Constitution. Here, the existence of the same rights in all areas of public and private life is recognized. Gender equality enshrined in the Constitution was only the first achievement of a long and arduous journey towards the affirmation of gender equality, which can be summarized in the following fundamental stages:

1950: the "Law for the physical and economic protection of working mothers" introduces the first maternity protections, prohibiting dismissal from the beginning of gestation until the first year of age of the offspring;

1963: the rules prohibiting dismissal in the event of marriage and Law no. 6/1963 are approved, which allows full equal access for women to professional careers, including the judiciary;

1975: Law No. 151 on the reform of family law establishes equality between spouses;

1977: approval of Law no. 903, which prohibits discrimination in access to employment, vocational training and wages;

1978: Women gain the right to abortion thanks to the adoption of Law No. 194;

1981: reparative marriage and honour killings are deleted from the Penal Code (Law n. 442);

2006: Legislative Decree no. 198 launches the Code of Equal Opportunities;

2019: the "Red Code" is adopted, which introduces the urgent procedure for crimes of gender and domestic violence, tightens the sanctioning framework, regulates new criminal cases (including revenge porn), provides for the training of police forces and the re-education of perpetrators of violence;

2021: Law n. 162 on gender equality in the workplace introduces certification for gender equality.

Since 2015, it is in force in Italy in the National Strategic Plan on Male Violence against Women, aimed at promoting prevention, protection of victims, punishment of aggressors, training and information.

However, continued commitment from government, institutions and civil society is needed to make meaningful and lasting changes.

In parallel with the regulations that have come into force in recent decades, specific action plans have been developed throughout the national territory and competences have been derived from the regions to create effective measures for the different

territories. We focus on the steps taken in this area by our Lombardia region. In 2017, local authorities approved lines of action in the fight against gender-based violence; in particular, the Regional Council approved the Four-Year Regional Plan for Equality Policies and the Prevention and Contrast to Violence against Women. The plan aims to promote a culture of equality and the recognition of fundamental human rights in the economic, social and family spheres. The regional action aims to consolidate all anti-violence centres and specialized structures in the area, and ensure effective prevention policies.

2. Gender representation in history in Italy

Gender representation in Italian history has undergone significant evolutions over time. However, it is important to recognize that until relatively recently, gender representation was heavily biased in favor of men in many spheres of society. Here's a look at different historical periods and how gender representation has been affected in Italy:

Ancient and medieval period. In ancient and medieval society, the role of women was often confined to the family and domestic sphere. Political, economic and cultural representation was dominated by men. However, some noble women or women from ruling families could exercise some degree of power, such as Cleopatra Selene II, Giudicessa Eleonora d'Arborea and other noble figures.

Renaissance. During the Italian Renaissance, some women had the opportunity to emerge in the cultural sphere. However, most of them were limited to roles of patrons or prominent figures within the noble courts. Some examples include Isabella d'Este, Lucrezia Borgia, and Vittoria Colonna.

XIX century and the unification of Italy. In the nineteenth century, with the rise of nationalist movements and the unification of Italy, women began to participate more actively in political and social debates. However, even in this period, the political participation of women was limited and often subordinate to that of men.

XX century. During the twentieth century, especially after World War II, women began to gain more opportunities for education and work. This gradually led to greater participation of women in various areas, including politics, work and education. However, gender inequalities persisted.

Contemporary period. In recent decades, Italy has seen a greater awareness of the importance of gender representation and equality. Laws have been adopted to promote

the presence of women in politics, company boards and other sectors. This has led to a gradual increase in the presence of women in leadership and representation roles.

In general, the history of gender representation in Italy has been characterized by gradual but significant progress. Despite historical challenges, Italian women have continued to struggle for greater visibility and participation in all sectors of society.

3. Female footprint in Italy

There have been many important women in Italian history who have contributed in various fields, including art, science, politics and culture. Here are some of them:

Cleopatra Selene II (c. 40 BC - c. 6 AD). Daughter of Cleopatra and Mark Antony, she was queen of Mauretania and played an important role in maintaining stable relations between Rome and her kingdom.

Artemisia Gentileschi (1593-1653). She was a renowned Baroque painter, famous for her emotionally powerful paintings and her struggle to be recognized as an artist in an era dominated by men.

Eleonora d'Arborea (1347-1404). She was a Sardinian political and legislator. Its laws, collected in the "Statute", are considered one of the first legislative codes in Europe written by a woman.

Maria Montessori (1870-1952). She was a pedagogue and physician, famous for her Montessori educational method that emphasizes autonomy and learning through direct experience.

Rita Levi-Montalcini (1909-2012). Neurologist, she was awarded the Nobel Prize in Medicine in 1986 for her discoveries regarding nerve cell growth factors.

Anna Magnani (1908-1973). She was a famous film actress, winner of an Academy Award, known for her intensity and authenticity on screen.

Nilde Iotti (1920-1999). She was an Italian politician and the first woman to be elected President of the Chamber of Deputies. She was a prominent figure in the Italian Communist Party.

Emma Bonino (born 1948): She was a leading figure in Italian politics, engaged in human rights, women's rights and foreign affairs issues.

Milena Gabanelli (born 1952): Journalist and television presenter, she is known for her commitment to journalistic investigation and investigative journalism.

These are just some of the remarkable women who have left a mark on Italian history. There are many other women who have contributed significantly in various fields and continue to do so.

As far as the specific territory of Lombardy and Lecco is concerned, there is an **absence or poor representation of female figures** in history. This deficiency is a common problem that reflects a broader historical tendency to underestimate or ignore women's contributions. This phenomenon can be attributed to several factors: gender stereotypes, in the past limited access to education and opportunities, selective storytelling.

The consequence is that in the territory of the San Martino Valley and the province of Lecco, the subject of the present research, there is a complete absence of knowledge about local female figures. This total absence is also reflected in a widespread lack of streets, monuments, squares, buildings dedicated to women.

Nevertheless, through an in-depth investigation, women have emerged who, in different historical moments, have contributed to the creation of the History of Lecco. These include:

- *Antonia Pozzi* (1912-1938): a poet and a writer who, through her works, was able to convey her love for nature and Como lake;
- *Antonietta Nava* (1912-2005): a teacher and principal for 46 years; she was also deputy mayor and municipal councillors;
- *Elena Gandolfi* (1945-2003): a language teacher and a researcher in the field of international adoptions; she's published some researches. As president of CIAI (Italian Centre for International Adoptions) she has worked nationally and internationally to promote bilateral pacts between governments and improve adoption legislation;
- *Piera Badoni* (1912-1989): a poet, with a great bond with the city of Lecco, she frequented great Italian writers and intellectuals;
- *Carla Acquistapace* (1918-2008): a member of the Communist Party, involved in women's defence groups in the reproduction of anti-fascist propaganda material and in the distribution of the clandestine press;
- *Zaira Spreafico* (1920-2004): she served as a volunteer Red Cross in military hospitals, she dedicated herself entirely to the Work of Don Luigi Monza, where she did her utmost

to assist abandoned children of the post-war period, orphans or children of executed and political prisoners;

- *Gabriella Zanini* (1921-2010): she carried out the first service aimed at terminally ill cancer patients in the Lecco area, establishing the ACMT association, engaged in the care of terminally ill patients.

Although the survey has highlighted the presence in history of female figures who have left an imprint on the Lecco area, there are no streets, squares or monuments named after them. Moreover, the citizens of the territory ignore the existence of these women and, if invited to think of the historical female figures of Lecco, only Lucia Mondella is mentioned, a fictitious character of the historical novel "I Promessi Sposi" by Alessandro Manzoni, set in Lecco.

4. City's practices in disseminating gender balanced history

The city of Lecco, located in Lombardia region, has a rich and fascinating history covering a long period of time. The diffusion of historical models in Lecco and, more generally, in the various Italian cities, takes place through different initiatives and resources, aimed at promoting a gender-balanced history, trying to give greater visibility to women and their contributions in history and society. Some of the practices adopted are:

Educational reforms: Italian schools are introducing more inclusive content into their curricula, highlighting women's accomplishments, and presenting a more balanced gender perspective in textbooks and teaching materials.

Cultural initiatives: cultural events and exhibitions have been organized to celebrate historical and contemporary female figures, highlighting their role in literature, art, science and other fields.

University curricula: Italian universities are expanding the offer of academic courses and programs that address gender issues, allowing students to delve into the history and role of women in society.

Cultural institutions: museums, art galleries and cultural institutions are working to ensure a more balanced representation of works of art and historical narratives that reflect women's experiences.

Research and publications: academics and researchers are studying and publishing stories that highlight the contributions of women in Italian and international history.

Women's Days: 8 March, International Women's Day, is an occasion in which Italy, like many other countries, celebrates and reflects on women's achievements and the challenges they face.

Political representation: Italy has adopted laws and gender quotas to promote the presence of women in municipal, regional and government councils, helping to ensure a more balanced representation in the political sphere.

Advertising and media: efforts are being made to avoid gender stereotypes and promote a more realistic and positive image of women in media and advertising.

Online initiatives and social media: online campaigns, hashtags and social platforms are used to highlight women's stories and gender issues, creating awareness and promoting dialogue.

These practices reflect a growing commitment to addressing the lack of balance in gender representation and historical narrative. However, there are still challenges to overcome to ensure a truly balanced and inclusive story that reflects the full range of human experiences, regardless of gender. The goal is to create an environment in which the past of Lecco and of every Italian city is valued and appreciated as a precious resource for the present and future of the city.

5. Local strategies

Starting from the gaps highlighted and the increasingly widespread desire to act concretely towards an effective change in the enhancement of female figures in history, in 2022 the city of Lecco promoted an initiative. On the month that hosts the International Day of Women's Rights, the Municipality has proposed to name its civic rooms after female characters linked to the history of the city and the territory. To do this, the municipal administration opened a survey aimed at citizens, with which it was possible to express their preferences among nine important women.

The decision to name the civic halls of the city after the women symbol of the territory was intended to be a recognition of the value of female protagonism. The civic halls were chosen because they represent the place of participation; Hence the commitment to encourage and strengthen the leading role of women.

Already in 2020, the young people of “AmbientalMente”, a Lecco civic political project that deals with environmental and social sustainability, gave voice to the theme through an innovative action. In fact, the boys and girls have symbolically changed the names of three streets in the city, naming them after as many great women in the history of our country. It was an initiative aimed at underlining the importance of gender equality and the fundamental role of women, unfortunately often underestimated if not forgotten even in Lecco. Counting the streets of the city, in fact, from the book "Lecco, the meaning of the streets from A to Z" it emerges that 233 streets are dedicated to men (including 18 characters of The Betrothed) and only eleven streets are dedicated to female figures (including 6 characters of The Betrothed). Through a survey, citizens were asked to choose three women from a list of ten important female figures. These are the results:

3rd place – Nilde Iotti, President of the Chamber (1920-1999)

2nd place – Francesca (Vera) Ciceri, anti-fascist and partisan from Lecco (1904-1988)

1st place – Lea Garofalo, victim of mafia (1974-2009)

With a flash mob the young people of “AmbientalMente” have flanked the original signs of toponymy, those dedicated to Lea Garofalo, Vera Ciceri and Nilde Iotti. A way to underline the value given to the concept of social sustainability, translated at this juncture into gender equality.

6. Focus Groups with Young People: Analyses and results

Students from two third-year classes of the Human Sciences High School at the L. Rota Institute in Calolziocorte were involved in the project. The students' age ranges from 16 to 18 years old.

These specific students were chosen because, within their school curriculum, they study subjects such as psychology, pedagogy, and sociology, which are closely related to the project's theme. This provides them with the opportunity to apply the theoretical knowledge and reflections on the gender theme in the present moment and in real-life situations.

Furthermore, these students have already experienced projects aimed at promoting the female figure, with a specific focus on the theme of the body, as well as narrative and communication experiences through radio channels. This has allowed them to address current issues relevant to the youth, including the topic of gender.

6.1. Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

Talking about women in history, through an initial brainstorming with the students, only female figures known at a national or international level are identified (for example, Rita Levi Montalcini, Frida Kahlo, Maria Montessori, ...). However, no figures related to the specific local territory emerge. Even when prompted to reflect on streets, places, squares, monuments, and parks dedicated to local women, the students report the absence of such references.

Therefore, a subsequent investigation was conducted, partially involving the students of the institute: through the use of the internet, interviews with acquaintances, and the analysis of street maps provided by local municipalities, they sought to find publicly recognized female figures in the territory. The results confirm what the students mentioned: there are no streets, parks, monuments, or roads dedicated to local women in our regions.

Conversely, when the students were invited to explore their family history, they recounted stories and narratives of ordinary women who had the opportunity to make a difference within the community. In this way, the young people came to understand that history is not only what is studied in books but is also shaped by individual actions in their daily lives.

Thinking about history, they express a desire to talk about the present: the history they have always encountered in the classroom has focused on a distant past that they do not perceive as their own or relevant to their current life context. Instead, they insist that history can also encompass the present or recent times.

6.2. Findings on 'Level of knowledge in history'

The students recognize that our small local territory, compared to larger cities, makes it more challenging to find female role models, both contemporary and historical.

Therefore, the search for women's footprints has involved various approaches. The students have interviewed family members and acquaintances of different ages, contacted mayors to access local street maps, conducted research through the internet, and consulted books and territorial guides. From all these sources, the total absence of recognized and publicly appreciated local women becomes evident.

6.3. Findings on 'Methods to promote women's footprint in history'

The students, invited to reflect on effective methods of promoting women's footprints in our territory, identify the following strategies.

One key tool is the use of various communication channels. Through mass media, it is possible to highlight narratives and give voice to stories and women's footprints, reaching populations of different ages and locations. Within these women's stories, a source of inspiration for the future, shared interests, and points of connection between generations can be found.

Art can also be employed as a means to address the theme. The students cite an example from the Municipality of Bellano, where 1700 inhabitants were captured in photographs displayed throughout the streets of the town, preserving their faces for the future. Building on this concept, the students envision a specific version of this initiative focused on valuing female figures from the local territory.

Furthermore, everyone can think of themselves as artists by creating drawings, poems, and songs through which they can express their interpretation of the theme and the importance of Her Story.

Finally, for the young students, it is essential to have concrete opportunities to meet these women. They recount how what they read in history books often feels distant from their own experiences. Therefore, having the chance to get to know local figures offers a tangible opportunity for knowledge and exchange.

7. Focus Groups with Stakeholders: Analyses and results

The discussion with the stakeholders took place initially through a focus group in which each of them could be presented; after that, together we reflected on the key issues of the project. Afterwards, each stakeholder was met individually, in order to deepen personal visions and experiences, as well skills and points of view relevant to Her Story Project.

Below the main nodes that emerged in the discussion.

7. 1 Findings on 'Relevance with the field of History'

In comparison to the historical dimension, stakeholders report the absence of historical female figures within the territory of Valle San Martino, the place under investigation. The only female figure closely linked to the territory of Lecco is that of Lucia Mondella, but she is a fictional character. Lucia is, in fact, the protagonist of the historical novel "The Betrothed" by Alessandro Manzoni, set precisely in the area of Lecco. Our women also observe how history, typically learned in schools, is based almost exclusively on the deeds of men, following an androcentric perspective. It is important, instead, to adopt a more inclusive viewpoint, even concerning traditional history.

The stakeholders emphasize the importance of focusing on the everyday stories of ordinary women, searching for what they define as the "silenced history." It is crucial to be able to see these women and their stories, giving them space, even just within the small contexts in which they lived or operated. For our women, the key lies in storytelling: to make known and spread these stories through different means and to diverse audiences.

According to our stakeholders, the history of a territory must now, more than ever, take into account a globalized world, where cultures meet, sometimes merging, while other times maintaining distinct and contrasting traits (some of them bring up the example of schools, where there are parents from non-Western cultures where the patriarchal dimension is still strong, requiring special attention).

Our women advocate the need for reflection on motherhood, understood as a life phase experienced by many, with its myriad facets. Becoming a mother, giving birth to a child, creates new balances and subtle connections; for some, it offers opportunities for self-discovery and a leap into new personal and professional experiences (as seen with our woman Romina); for others, it represents a "necessary" stage to be a woman, to understand a woman/mother; for yet others, it becomes an obstacle to their professional career, where they may need to "scale down the hierarchy" after having a child; and for someone else, it becomes a social pressure, an almost obligatory stage in the eyes of others, limiting their drive, creating feelings of inadequacy and lack.

Regarding this topic, it is also essential to provide equal space and knowledge of the rights and responsibilities of both mothers and fathers, promoting awareness of the law and breaking old stereotypes.

7.2 Findings on 'History through the lens of their expertise'

The sharing of their personal, professional, and lived experiences, along with acquired skills and viewpoints, by the stakeholders has led to reflections that intertwine the past and the present.

Each of them highlights how the place and historical period in which one is born and raised leave a strong imprint on each individual; it is a contextual dimension that profoundly influences a person's development. Family and family history, more or less anchored to traditional educational and cultural patterns, have influenced their academic, work, and personal growth paths.

The specific territorial dimension in which they were born and raised, the Valle San Martino and more generally the province of Lecco, represent small, still "closed" territories that have engendered a reciprocal exchange: while the territory provides support, closeness, and a sense of belonging, creating a strong bond, in each woman, there arises a desire to actively contribute to its care and enhancement.

According to our women, history is constructed through concrete models capable of influencing, sometimes even unconsciously, someone's choices. Our teacher Alessandra gives the example of the school where she teaches, where out of 40 teachers, there is only one man. This absence of male figures does not offer male children the opportunity to recognize themselves in their own gender and in the opposite one. Consequently, even among professionals, an opportunity for exchanging ideas and different perspectives is lost.

In their experiences of growth, our women recognize the importance of travel as an opportunity for meeting, comparison, and openness to others and differences. While travel provides a chance to learn about new models, cultures, and stories, the constant exchange diminishes the individuality of each of them and creates a sense of homogeneity (this dimension is even more pronounced today due to globalization and mass media).

7.3 Findings on 'Experience with young people in the field of History'

Over the years, controversial thoughts have arisen regarding the construction of gender, but undoubtedly, it stems from a social division that changes over time and space, conditioning people's thoughts and actions. Gender is situated within a complex sex/gender system: the sex category, which in animal species refers to purely physical and innate characteristics related to reproduction, in the human species delves into a

socio-cultural structure that is determinant. Currently, there exist different roles that classify customs and practices into expressions of femininity and masculinity. At birth, each individual is assigned a gender identity that will be expanded throughout life, actively and passively, through messages and behaviors.

According to our stakeholders, it is important to take active action to change the sex/gender dichotomy that has developed throughout history in all societies worldwide and positions women in a particular condition in the social hierarchy. To achieve this, the most effective method for them is engaging with the younger generations: having conversations with boys and girls, creating opportunities for exchange, and together modeling new practices and references.

Our teacher Alessandra presents the experience of the association of which she is the president, "L'Isola della Stupidera": this space not only offers help to children in their extracurricular educational activities but also constitutes a shared and educational experience. Every day, high school boys are involved as educators, a profession typically associated with female figures; the aim is, on one hand, to let boys also experience a role of care and education, and on the other hand, to offer children male figures who embody that role. The keywords of "L'Isola della Stupidera" are, therefore: looking, valuing, seeing, opening, and broadening horizons.

Fulvia, a member of Soroptimis, a free association of women engaged in professional and managerial activities in various fields of society, shares the initiative "SifaSTEM." It is a university orientation project for female students interested in STEM subjects (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). The goal is to motivate girls to pursue their dreams, free from prejudices, and to courageously dare to pursue scientific training paths. The world of work greatly needs technical knowledge. Fulvia emphasizes the need to break down gender biases concerning STEM subjects, increase the number of girls in STEM fields, and help them make informed choices not dictated by society's concepts and stereotypes.

7.4 Findings on 'Women's footprint in History'

The stakeholders highlight the absence, within the territory under investigation, of "traces" of women in different historical epochs. According to them, this absence can be traced back to a historical-cultural dimension that has always been based on the valorization of typically male and heroic models, while giving little recognition to the everyday, simple but fundamental actions of ordinary women.

One cause of this absence can be found in the limited female participation in social life. Throughout history, the social construction of gender has kept public and private spaces separate, assigning the former to men and the latter to women. Thus, women have always been recognized for their caregiving roles in the private sphere, but these actions have remained invisible to society. During the particular period of industrialization, this dichotomy became even more accentuated, with notions of "political, power, community, public" attributed solely to men.

In the last few decades, the feminist movements of the 1960s and 1970s have advocated for the need to analyze women's conditions in the past, breaking away from the traditional framework of an androcentric historical discipline. To overcome these limitations, feminism has introduced new methods, concepts, and categories capable of giving voice to women and social groups that were previously silenced.

Our women view history as a continuum between the past, present, and future. From this perspective, the footprints of women today become a fundamental tool for change in the future. It is essential to value the meaningful experiences of women today, moving beyond the gender dimension and focusing instead on individuality and uniqueness. To generate such a change, a key role must be given to families and educational contexts that accompany the growth of children from a very young age.

7.5 Suggestions from participants on female footprint in the city/in history

Le stakeholders emphasize the importance of giving voice: narrating, telling stories, and actively involving the new generations. This allows for creating cross-cutting communication that reaches individuals of all ages and communities, both men and women. In this way, it is possible to value the footprints in local territories and throughout different moments in history. Furthermore, according to our women, it is crucial to free every individual from old traditional gender stereotypes. This means that this issue should not remain solely the concern of women. It is essential to recognize that men also have the power to bring about change in this regard. Not all men are necessarily the sole providers of the family's economic well-being, or the ones who are physically and emotionally strong. They are complex and unique individuals who go beyond these stereotypes, just as women do. To break free from the societal weight of gender differences, it is vital to highlight the individuality of each one of us and leave new footprints capable of creating new stories.

By breaking down gender stereotypes and recognizing the unique qualities and abilities of every individual, we can foster a more inclusive and equal society where both men

and women have the opportunity to thrive and contribute positively to their communities. This approach leads to a more profound understanding of each other's experiences, challenges, and aspirations, ultimately working towards a more equitable and harmonious world.

8. Conclusions

As emerges from this desk research, the territory of Valle San Martino and Lecco still shows a great absence of female historical references. The few identified are not known and it is difficult to find information about them. Hence the desire and the need, starting from HerStory project, to deal with present history, to enhance the experiences of contemporary women.

Focusing on the present, through ordinary women with whom it is possible to interact, we intend to create a new knowledge, involving the entire community in the theme. Offer boys and girls spaces for dialogue and comparison with these female figures, letting them become for them a source of inspiration, reflection and sharing. Making young people protagonists allows us to open new horizons capable of creating new models, new good practices, new knowledge and new points of view that become baggage for the future of the individual and of society as a whole.

